

Table S1-A: forward and reverse primers of Up-regulated genes used in *qRT-PCR*.

<i>Primer Name</i>	<i>Primer Sequence (5'to3')</i>	
	Forward	Reverse
<i>COL6A1</i>	TCAAGAGCCTGCAG-TGGATG	TGGACACTTCTTGTCT-ATGCAG
<i>PTK7</i>	GATGGAATGCCTCAACGGT	CAAACACTCTTCCCCAGC
<i>COL8A1</i>	ACCCAAGAAAGGCAAAGAAATA	TTAATTCCAGGTATCCCATGAC
<i>ANXA6</i>	AGCATCTTCGGTTGGTGTT	CGGATACACTTCACTACGGC
<i>NID1</i>	CAACCACCATCATTAGACAAGA	GGATTCACCAAGTCAGTCTCAA
<i>CDH5</i>	CTACCAGCCCAAAGTGTGTGA	CGTGTTATCGTGATTATCCGTG
<i>SPOCK1</i>	TGCGAACAGAGTCATCAAGC	ACAGGGCTCGTACTTATCCAG
<i>PTPRM</i>	ACAGACAAACTCAAGCCAGATT	ATTGATGTAGTTGCTGCTCTCC
<i>HLA-B</i>	TGCTGTGATGTGTAGGAGGAAG	AGGGGAGGCGTGAAGAAAT
<i>CDH11</i>	CATCGTCATTCTCCTGGGTT	CCACCACATAGAGGAAAGGAAG

Table S1-B: forward and reverse primers of Down-regulated genes used in *qRT-PCR*.

<i>Primer Name</i>	<i>Primer Sequence (5'to3')</i>	
	Forward	Reverse
<i>LY6D</i>	GCTCCCAGACGACATCAGA	AGAGGCTCCACTGTGTTCCG
<i>KLK11</i>	TGTAGGGGGGAGAGACCAGGAT	CAGGTGAACTATGTAGCGGGG
<i>SYT8</i>	GAGACCTGCTGCTTCCACAT	ACCAGTGCTCCAGAACATGC
<i>TRIM31</i>	ATTCAAAGACCAACTCCAGGC	GGGCTGAAGAGTGGTGATTT
<i>UPK3B</i>	TATCGGGTGAAGTTCCTCCT	CTTGGTGGAGAGTGATGGG
<i>WNT10A</i>	GGGTGCTCCTGTTCTTCTACT	ACGCACACACACCTCCATCT
<i>TNNI2</i>	AAGGAGGACACAGAGAAGGAGC	AGGACTCGGACTCAAACATCTT
<i>MYH14</i>	CGGCTGTTTACCAAGGTGAAG	CACACAGTTCTGCCTCTGCTC
<i>SCD</i>	CCCCTACGGCTCTTTCTGAT	TAGCGTACTCCCCTTCTCTTTG
<i>CRIP1</i>	ATGCCCAAGTGTCCCAAGT	CAGCGTCTCCACATTTCTC

Table S1-C: β -actin forward and reverse primers sequence used in *qRT-PCR*.

<i>Primer Name</i>	<i>Primer Sequence (5'to3')</i>	
	Forward	Reverse
β -actin	AGCGAGCATCCCCAAAGTT	GGGCACGAAGGCTCATCATT